

A Crossbar-based coherent silicon photonic MIMO processor for wireless communications

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Abstract: We demonstrate a silicon photonic coherent MIMO processor using a photonic Crossbar (Xbar) layout. Successful experimental validation of its performance as a 4×4 MIMO processor and a 3×3 MIMO with on-chip phase retrieval is presented. © 2024 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Wireless systems are indisputably considered as the backbone of communications networks, though the continuously increasing bandwidth, throughput and capacity demands pose a challenge in the development of future 5G/6G infrastructure [1]. On this route, multiple input multiple output (MIMO) systems hold a crucial role for establishing both proper routing of the transmitted signal across the network nodes and signal quality metrics compliant to industrial standards. Photonic systems emerged as a favorable platform for MIMO processors in the emerging 6G communication sector due to their high bandwidth, improved energy efficiency and small footprint credentials, with several demonstrations reported in the last decade [2-6]. Since matrix-vector multiplications comprise the fundamental operation of MIMO processors, coherent photonic architectures utilizing Mach-Zehnder Interferometric (MZI) meshes and singular value decomposition (SVD) schemes, have been extensively studied and adapted in microwave photonics systems. However, such coherent architectures suffer from non-restorable fidelity metrics and an exponential insertion loss (IL) growth when scaling up the photonic circuitry dimensions [7-9], severely constraining their potential for large scale photonic MIMO applications.

In this paper, we introduce a silicon photonic MIMO processor that incorporates a coherent photonic Xbar as the backbone optical processor [7-9]. The proposed layout allows the cancellation of any linear channel by applying its inverse response on the received signals through a direct matrix-to-hardware mapping procedure, in contrast with other photonic demonstrations that operate solely with unitary transfer matrices and respective matrix decomposition schemes. The experimental demonstration of a 4×4 and a 3×3 MIMO processor is presented, designed for the demultiplexing of single RF tones in the range of 7.5 to 15 GHz, with worst case suppression ratio being equal to 10.7 dB. Moreover, the Xbar-based photonic MIMO processor architecture allows for an on-chip optical adaptive phase restoration mechanism that negates the need for electronic Phase Locked Loop (PLL)-based phase error correction modules; this is experimentally verified by modifying the phase of the optical carrier prior its re-insertion, indicatively achieving RF phase tuning equivalent to time delays of ± 0.01 ns. Given the theoretically and experimentally confirmed loss and fidelity benefits of the photonic Xbar linear operator with respect to respective SVD-based MZI meshes, its successful deployment as a MIMO processor for wireless communications can in principle pave the road for scalable photonic MIMO prototypes for 6G communications.

2. The coherent Xbar MIMO processor

The layout of the $N \times N$ Xbar MIMO processor, designed for applications in wireless communication networks, is presented in Fig. 1. Conceptually, an array of N antennas is used to transmit N RF signals, expressed in vector form as $\mathbf{T}_N = [T_1(t), \dots, T_N(t)]$. Under the assumption that the underlying communication channel is linear, and therefore expressed as an $N \times N$ matrix \mathbf{C} , the antennas on the receiver side will capture a linear combination of all N signals, expressed in vector form as $\mathbf{R}_N = [R_1(t), \dots, R_N(t)]$ and produced by the matrix-vector product $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{C} \cdot \mathbf{T}$. In order to circumvent the effect of the linear channel, a zero forcing method can be adapted to demultiplex any of the originally transmitted signals on demand, by performing the inverse linear transformation of the channel on the received signals, expressed as a matrix \mathbf{C}^{-1} . In the proposed scheme, an $N \times N$ Xbar is introduced after the reception of the RF signals, allowing the implementation of the \mathbf{C}^{-1} matrix in the optical domain through proper tuning of the Xbar nodes, each incorporating an amplitude modulator (AM) and a phase shifter (PS). Introducing a single sideband (SSB) filter at the Xbar outputs allows the optical carrier to beat with only one of the two signal's sidebands at the photodiode (PD), producing in this way the targeted RF carrier at the PD output.

The Xbar layout can also support a carrier reinsertion path by splitting the continuous wave (CW) beam towards an additional bias branch b_c , prior to the initial $1 \times N$ splitting stage. This path includes a dedicated PS for each Xbar column, so that the part of the optical carrier that enters the bias branch can be tuned in phase before recombining

Fig. 1: Principle of operation for the $N \times N$ Xbar MIMO processor. By reversing the effect of a linear channel C through a zero forcing approach, the coherent photonic circuit allows the demultiplexing of the received signals R , obtaining the originally transmitted signals T . The introduction of carrier-reinsertion paths to the outputs of the photonic Xbar, each equipped with an independent PS, permits the restoration of any arbitrary time delay introduced by the photonic system.

with the Xbar column output signal. This allows the compensation of any possible phase variation in the RF wireless domain, offering an on-chip phase retrieval and synchronization mechanism for the RF wireless signal without requiring the Phase Locked Loop (PLL)-based elements typically employed within the electronic digital signal processing (DSP) chain [5].

3. Experimental setup and results

The setup deployed for the experimental demonstration of the Xbar MIMO processor is presented in Fig. 2(a). A laser source, set at 1561.12 nm, was used to generate the CW beam that was injected into the Si-photonic integrated circuit (PIC). The PIC comprised a 4×4 Xbar with 50 GHz GeSi electro-absorption modulators (EAM) as input AMs, supporting high speed data transmission [9]. The input EAMs were externally driven by a four-channel, 60 GSa/s Keysight 8195 arbitrary waveform generator (AWG), producing signals with amplitude in the range of 2-3 V_{pp}, enabled by 67 GHz RF amplifiers. Similarly, the Xbar nodes encompassed EAMs and thermo-optical PSs, which were externally tuned through a multi-port digital to analog (DAC) converter. More details regarding the specifications and losses of the Xbar silicon chip can be found in [9]. The optical output of the PIC was amplified by an erbium doped amplifier (EDFA) and sequentially directed to a Finisar WaveShaper 4000a (WS) module that implements the SSB filtering stage, with central wavelength, bandwidth and IL equal to 1561.2 nm, 0.2 nm and 6 dB respectively. Finally, the filtered signal was captured by a 75 GHz photodiode (PD) and was processed either by a Keysight N9040B signal analyzer or by a 70 GHz digital sampling oscilloscope. Additional components, such as isolators (ISO), optical band pass filters (BPF) and polarization controllers (PC) were incorporated in the setup to ensure the optical signal integrity of the transmitted signals.

The Xbar layout was first evaluated as a 4×4 Xbar MIMO processor, with the results summarized in Fig. 2(b). Specifically, four tones resembling ideally transmitted signals with equal amplitudes, with frequencies equal to 7.5,

Fig. 2: (a) Experimental setup for the demonstration of a 4×4 MIMO processor, incorporating a 4×4 Xbar. (b) The experimental demultiplexed signals, with experimental crosstalk exceeding 11.3 dB for all cases.

Fig. 3: (a) Operation of 4×4 Xbar as a 3×3 MIMO processor, where the fourth row operates as a carrier re-insertion path b_c . (b) Demultiplexing signals at the outputs of the Xbar, with experimental crosstalk being always better than 10.7 dB. (c) Multiplexed and demultiplexed 10 GHz signal traces at the output of the Xbar. (d) Introduced time delay at the demultiplexed output, when tuning the phase shifter of the carrier reinsertion paths b_c in different states. The DC level shift of the recovered signals is compensated during post-processing.

10, 12 and 15 GHz, respectively, were multiplexed through a 4×4 linear channel C to produce different linear combinations with non-trivial time delays. These four linear combinations were then generated by the respective AWG electrical channels and were fed to the X -input EAMs of the Xbar. The Xbar nodes were then tuned in order to implement the inverted C^{-1} matrix in the optical domain and isolate each of the four tones at a different Xbar output. As shown in Fig. 2(b), the suppression ratio between the demultiplexed and the suppressed tones was greater than 11.3 dB for all cases. The suppression ratio can be further improved by using MZI modulators instead of EAMs in the Xbar architecture, so that a higher extinction ratio is obtained at every X - and W -matrix node.

The on-chip phase retrieval and synchronization capabilities of the Xbar-based MIMO processor were then evaluated by implementing a 3×3 MIMO processor and utilizing the 4th Xbar row as the bias branch, with the layout and respective results being summarized in Fig. 3. In this scheme, three tones with equal amplitudes and frequencies 10, 12 and 15 GHz were multiplexed through a 3×3 matrix C , emulating in this way the linear wireless channel. The 3 channel outputs were then generated by respective AWG electrical channels and were used to drive three of the Xbar X -input EAMs. The 3×3 matrix section of the Xbar was then configured to realize C^{-1} , successfully leading to the three demultiplexed tones at the three Xbar outputs with a suppression ratio being in all cases higher than exceeding 10.7 dB, as shown in Fig. 3(b). The successful demultiplexing operation is also illustrated in the time domain in Fig. 3(c), where the linear combination of the three tones (red) transforms to a clear 10 GHz sinusoidal tone (blue). By tuning then the PS of the carrier reinsertion path at every respective Xbar output, the RF phase of the demultiplexed tone can be varied to compensate for possible RF phase drifts and variations in the wireless channel. This is demonstrated in Fig. 3(d) for the demultiplexed 10 GHz tone, where three time-delayed replicas of the 10 GHz signal are illustrated. Each time delay corresponds to a different phase shift enforced at the carrier reinsertion path. Fig. 3(d) depicts indicative time delays of ± 0.01 ns that correspond to phase shifts of $\pm 36^\circ$ and were obtained for current values equal to 5 and 15 mA, respectively, applied to the PS in the Xbar carrier reinsertion path.

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